

CREATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AS AN EFFECTIVE
WAY TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' COMPETENCE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6506778>

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Abstract: *This article scientifically analyzes the role and importance of creative pedagogical technologies in the development of competencies of students of higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *intellect, pedagogical technologies, creativity, expertise, qualimetry, didactic support, control.*

The global external challenges of the innovative development of the economy and society place new demands on the education system. These requirements include the training of specialists capable of self-realization in labor and social activities in the innovative environment of the future. Intelligence, ability for creative activity, entrepreneurial and managerial skills in the society of the XXI century. become the most important characteristics of competitiveness and success of a person.

The formation of the above characteristics of graduates is possible with competence-based training, where the educational process is implemented on the basis of an educational and creative plan and educational and methodological complexes in integrative disciplines and is characterized by the following didactic features: providing psychological and pedagogical conditions for individualized learning, pedagogical stimulation of the rhythm of performing research work , targeted focus on the formation and development of the experience of scientific presentations, the priority use of research teaching methods, the creation of conditions for the active acquisition of creative experience in solving urgent professional problems, the use of diagnostic methods at different stages of education, an orientation towards continuous creative training of masters, the use of qualimetric indicators for evaluating effectiveness educational process.

The implementation of these features is possible on the basis of the introduction of creative pedagogical technologies, all components of which are aimed at the formation, development and formation of an independent creative personality of the student (Pic. 1)

Pic.1 The structure of creative pedagogical technology

Consider the didactic and methodological features of conducting classroom lectures, implemented using creative pedagogical technology.

Of the many types of lectures for creative pedagogical technologies, the most productive and effective are problem lectures that improve the quality of assimilation of theoretical material by students. To quantify the quality of problematic lectures, qualimetric criteria for the effective use of didactic resources (indicators of the use of time, information and creative resources) have been developed and mathematical models have been created to determine these criteria.

Seminars in competency-based training are held in the form of creative seminars with the following didactic features: individualization of seminar questions, regulation of the student's speech, allowing all seminar participants to speak, efficient use of time resources, stimulation of the preparation and implementation of creative speeches¹. The quality of the seminar is evaluated according to two qualimetric criteria: an indicator of the activity and creativity of students' speeches.

The relationship of these indicators reflects the degree of use of time resources and the quality of students' performances. With high values of these indicators, it can be stated that the planning, preparation and conduct of the seminar by the teacher were carried out at a high level, which was reflected in the number of creative performances of students.

The main functions of students' self-study during competency-based training: active formation of the experience of an analytical approach to the perception and

¹ Tolipov U.K., Usmanbayeva M. Pedagogical technology: theory and practice: Monograph. -T.: "Science", 2005. - 206 p.

comprehension of information in lectures; active acquisition of skills and abilities to use the methods of scientific and applied research in solving practical problems; acquisition of skills and experience of self-organization, self-management, self-analysis and self-assessment of the results of independent work; development of experience in solving various practice-oriented problems based on heuristic and creative thinking; development of experience in a responsible attitude to the process and results of solving professional and humanitarian problems of varying complexity.

Competence-based control is aimed at determining the levels of acquired competency facets and at consistent (input and semester diagnostics) determining the levels of development of these facets. Semester diagnostics, implemented after the end of each semester, make it possible to identify the dynamics of the formation of competence levels in the process of educational and creative activities of students.